

ISic1439

I.Sicily inscription 1439

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

epigram

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

04.10.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 7735

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329628

1. κα[ι] προγόνο̄.

2.

Edition: PHI330082

1. τᾶς ἁγία θ-

2. υγατρός εἰμι ²⁷εἰμ[ι] (Guarducci)²⁷

3. Καπρογόνο̄.

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644982

EDCS 64800232

PHI 329628

PHI 330082

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1439. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385938>